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**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING
AND SOCIAL ADAPTATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF WAR: A
STUDY ON THE EXAMPLE OF INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS
IN UKRAINE**

**ВЗАЄМОЗВ'ЯЗОК ПСИХОЛОГІЧНОГО БЛАГОПОЛУЧЧЯ І
СОЦІАЛЬНОЇ АДАПТАЦІЇ В УМОВАХ ВІЙНИ: ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ НА
ПРИКЛАДІ ВИМУШЕНИХ ПЕРЕСЕЛЕНЦІВ УКРАЇНИ**

Існує взаємозв'язок між психологічним благополуччям та соціальною адаптацією переміщених осіб, які постраждали від війни, що триває в Україні. Досвід війни впливає на психологічне благополуччя людей, зокрема на їхній емоційний стан та здатність адаптуватися до нового життя. Дослідження включало комплексний аналіз факторів, що впливають на психологічне благополуччя та соціальну адаптацію у вибірці з 72 осіб віком від 17 до 49 років, серед яких 54 жінки та 18 чоловіків.

Ключові слова: психологічне благополуччя, соціальна адаптація, війна, Україна, переселенці.

At the current stage in the history of Ukraine, war is a driving force for population displacement, which creates an extremely urgent problem related to the psychological well-being and social and psychological adaptation of internally and externally displaced persons in our country. Staying in the conflict zone, loss of residence and constant threat to life create serious psychological challenges and force people to adapt to a new life in a different socio-cultural environment. Understanding the relationship between psychological well-being and social adaptation in war conditions allows us to better assess the key aspects of adaptation and psychological support for this vulnerable population. In this regard, it is important to review the results of our research and determine how psychological well-being affects the social adaptation of internally and externally displaced persons.

Psychological well-being has a close influence on social adaptation. Psychological well-being is a state in which a person feels satisfied with his or her life, controls his or her behaviour and emotions, and has the ability to adapt to new situations. Psychological well-being has two main components: the prevalence of positive emotions over negative ones and a positive assessment of one's life.

The main way to achieve psychological well-being is through successful social adaptation – adapting to real conditions, situations and requirements of the social environment. Social and psychological adaptation is a process by which an

individual meets the requirements of the social environment and integrates well into it. The indicators of social and psychological adaptation are self-esteem, effectiveness of a person's entry into society, recognition or non-recognition by others, the presence of friends, features of formal and informal communication, and the level of satisfaction of their communication needs. (Melnik O.V., Lukomska S.O.,2018)

The study was conducted in 2022-2023 and included four main stages. The first stage consisted of defining the subject and object of the study, formulating the research topic and setting the main research objectives, which reflected the issues of internally and externally displaced persons in the context of the war in Ukraine. The second stage included a theoretical analysis and synthesis of literature, selection of research methods, and organisation of the research itself. The third stage consisted of conducting the study, during which the hypotheses set for the research were evaluated. The fourth stage included mathematical and statistical processing of the data obtained and their interpretation, as well as drawing conclusions and presenting the results of the study. The experiment involved 72 internally and externally displaced persons, aged 17 to 49 years, with 54 women and 18 men. Several methods were used to assess the relationship between socio-psychological adaptation and psychological well-being of internally displaced persons:

1. Basic Values Satisfaction Scale: determined the psychological characteristics and conditions of forming the image of the city in the mind of the individual as an adaptation resource.

2. The «Life in a new city» methodology: determined the psychological well-being of individuals in a new city by assessing the factors of comfort, aesthetics, naturalness, modernity, simplicity and dynamism.

3. Rogers and Diamond's Psychosocial Adaptation Inventory: examined personality traits related to psychosocial adaptation, including adaptability, acceptance of others, internalising, self-awareness, emotional comfort, and desire for control.

4. The K. Riffe Psychological Well-Being Scale: provided information on the level of subjective well-being and its individual components.

The study examined the relationship between psychological well-being and socio-psychological adaptation among internally displaced persons during the war in Ukraine. In the analysis of the relationship between the level of well-being and adaptation indicators, two poles of psychological well-being were identified: high and low levels.

The study participants who had a high level of psychological well-being were characterised by a greater ability to perceive themselves and others positively. They demonstrated emotional comfort and inner stability. These people did not seek to dominate others, but had inner determination and independence in decision-making. Their lives were defined by a positive perception of the world around them and a belief in their own abilities.

In contrast, participants with low levels of psychological well-being showed higher levels of maladjustment, negative attitudes towards themselves and others, emotional discomfort, and a higher tendency to external control. They experienced significant stress and negative emotions and tended to feel that their lives were controlled by external circumstances and other people. These people tend to submit to others, accept their demands and decisions without much objection or resistance. They also showed a lack of initiative and determination to solve life's problems, sought escape to an alternative reality, and believed that their lives were affected by external circumstances.

The study also analysed the correlation between psychological well-being and adaptability in the context of forced displacement as a result of the war in Ukraine. High levels of adaptability were found to be significantly associated with positive aspects of psychological well-being. This includes the development of positive relationships with others, increased autonomy and the ability to control one's environment. People with high adaptability are also more likely to experience personal growth, feel more valued, have a life purpose, and have positive self-acceptance. In contrast, individuals with lower adaptability may have more difficulty establishing positive relationships with others, maintaining autonomy and control over their lives. They may experience less satisfaction from personal growth and achievement, as well as more stress and negative emotions. Such people usually experience less harmony and satisfaction in their lives.

The study found various correlations between indicators of social and psychological adaptability and the level of psychological well-being among IDPs. The data obtained as a result of the study allow us to identify both positive and negative relationships between the indicators.

Positive correlations showed that a high level of adaptability correlates with greater autonomy and a sense of control over the environment, with greater personal growth and the importance of life goals. People with high levels of adaptability have positive self-acceptance, and as the level of deceitfulness increases, their responses become more open and honest.

Negative correlations indicated that positive relationships with others were negatively correlated with maladjustment. Decreased autonomy, life purpose, personal growth, and control were associated with increased maladjustment. Submissiveness and problem avoidance can lead to a decrease in internal control, life purpose, self-acceptance, and overall psychological well-being.

In conclusion, IDPs who have a high level of psychological well-being and adaptability have positive internal resilience, positive attitudes towards themselves and others, and the ability to manage their lives effectively. In contrast, those with low levels of psychological well-being and adaptability tend to have negative attitudes, stress and a sense of loss of control over their lives.

In other words, we can say that the experiment reveals a deep and complex relationship between psychological well-being and social adaptation among IDPs affected by the war in Ukraine. The information in the form of results helps to

better understand the impact of war and internal displacement on psychological resilience and the ability of individuals to adapt to their new lives. The findings can help in the development of programmes and initiatives for psychological support and rehabilitation of IDPs. Understanding how to improve psychological well-being and promote social adaptation can help reduce the difficulties people face.